

AGROVOLTAICS TECHNOLOGY IN AGRICULTURE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *Agrovoltaics is an innovative technology that combines agriculture with solar energy production to generate electricity. Installing solar panels over agricultural fields allows farms to generate clean energy while simultaneously growing crops, maximizing land efficiency. Locally generating electricity reduces dependence on fossil fuels and external energy grids, as well as water consumption, making farms more sustainable and cost-effective.*

Keywords: *agrovoltaics, innovative technology, agriculture, crop, solar energy, insolation, solar panel, photovoltaics, photosynthesis, shading, crop yield, electricity generation.*

Introduction

Modern agriculture increasingly consumes electricity as farmers utilize advanced electricity-powered technologies, such as various agricultural machinery, automated irrigation systems, and other high-precision equipment. With the electrification of agricultural machinery and the use of drones for crop management, farmers' energy needs will increase significantly in the future [1-5]. Agrivoltaics can meet these needs by providing farmers with a stable, renewable energy source (RES) through the installation of solar panels, thereby reducing dependence on fossil fuels and external energy grids, making farms more efficient.

Extreme heat and drought adversely affect the quality and yield of agricultural crops. Shading created by photovoltaic panels (PVP) can reduce soil moisture evaporation by up to 30 percent, significantly reducing water consumption and enabling more efficient use of water resources, especially in areas with limited water supplies [6-8]. Agrivoltaics, also known as agrophotovoltaics, is an innovative technological solution for simultaneously using land for agricultural production and generating solar energy. This is achieved by installing translucent PVP over crops, allowing plants to receive sunlight and retain soil moisture, increasing yields while simultaneously generating electricity.

The concept of agrovoltaics was proposed in 1982 by German scientists A. Goetzberger and A. Zastrow as a means of modifying solar power plants to increase crop yields. Their idea was to raise the PVP above the ground and increase the distance between them to avoid excessive shading of crops [15]. Researching the experience of other countries, it can be noted that in India, the PVP capacity on 34000 hectares of vineyards is 16000 GWh. This covers the electricity needs of 15 million residents. It has also been estimated that the 0.47 GWh of electricity generated by the PVP on one hectare is sufficient to power 500 people. Research conducted in the Arizona desert (USA) has proven that growing certain crops under PVP reduces water consumption by 30-50 percent. Furthermore, in arid conditions, soil fertility and crop yields are maintained year-round. In China, the largest solar thermal power plant to date, with a capacity of 700 MW, was commissioned in 2017 at a medicinal plantation in the Ningxia Hui Autonomous Region. According to experts from Baofeng Group and Huawei, the project will save 557600 tons of coal

fuel per year and prevent the emission of approximately two million tons of harmful substances and dust into the atmosphere [12-16].

As of 2022, the global PVP market was worth \$3.17 billion. This figure is expected to grow by 12-15 percent annually, reaching nearly \$9 billion by 2030. According to other sources, the average annual growth rate of this new technology could reach at least 40 percent by 2027 [5,6]. Agrovoltaic technology is based on a physical process in PVP, the external photovoltaic effect, in which photons generate electrons in a semiconductor material. Agrovoltaic systems (AVS) operate on the physical principles of solar energy conversion, heat balance, moisture evaporation, and light distribution. The well-known "Brite Solar" AVS, where translucent PVP contain special nanoparticles that optimize light management by converting ultraviolet radiation into the red spectrum, which is most beneficial for photosynthesis (*Figure 1.*) [9].

Figure 1. Brite Solar agrovoltaic systems

Over the past decades, Uzbekistan has faced a number of environmental and economic challenges: limited water and land resources, soil degradation, rising energy consumption, and dependence on fossil fuels. At the same time, the country possesses significant solar energy potential - an average of 300 sunny days per year, equivalent to approximately 2000-3000 hours of sunshine per year. This potential enables the generation of over 50 billion kWh of electricity annually (*Table 1.*), making solar energy one of the most promising areas for RES [5-7].

Table 1. Solar energy potential in Uzbekistan

Energy type	Potential power	Regional characteristics
Solar energy	More than 50 billion kWh per year	Almost all regions of the republic have up to 300 sunny days per year, and the average annual solar energy per square meter of land surface is 1600–1800 kWh/m ²

Given the need to diversify the agricultural and energy sectors of the Republic, agrovoltaics represents an innovative technological solution that can significantly improve the environmental and economic aspects of the problem [8].

Methods and materials

The basis of agrovoltaics is insolation, the specialized and natural irradiation of the earth's surface with sunlight. According to the insolation level map for the regions of Central Asia, the insolation level is 4.0 - 4.9 (*Figure 2.*). Accordingly: average annual insolation is 1600–1800 kWh/m²; the number of sunny days is 240-300 per year; the moisture evaporation rate is up to 10 mm/day due to high temperatures from +40 to +50°C.

Figure 2. Map of the earth's insolation level

Figure 3. Insolation graph

The presented insolation graph of Russia (Figure 3.) allows us to estimate the temperature balance (from +30°C to +40°C) in various regions of the country with a hot climate, while the active insolation period averages 5-6 months. The greatest potential for the development of solar thermal units was demonstrated in regions with a tropical and sharply continental climate - in the Rostov Region, Krasnodar and Altai Krai, where they generated 18610 kWh, 20613 kWh, and 20415 kWh of electricity per year, respectively. Depending on the region, the levelized cost of energy generated by the PVP also varies from 0.016 \$ to 0.032 \$ per kWh. The data obtained prove the high potential and motivation for the development of solar thermal units in the above-mentioned regions of Russia [9].

In almost all regions of Uzbekistan, the active insolation period with a temperature balance from +35°C to 45°C averages 7-8 months. The most promising regions for the implementation of agrovoltatics are Navoi, Bukhara, Kashkadarya, Khorezm regions, and Karakalpakstan.

The implementation of agrovoltaic systems in these regions can significantly mitigate the negative impact of soil and plant overheating, maintaining the water balance and generating electricity for their own needs.

The installation of translucent PVP in these regions at a height of 2-5 meters, with intervals allowing sunlight to penetrate and simultaneously shading the soil, will significantly positively impact soil parameters (Table 2.) and crop yields (Figure 4.) [17,18].

Table 2. Parameters and effect of PVP shading

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Effect when shading at 20-30%</i>
Soil temperature	From +4°C to +6°C
Water consumption	Decrease by 15-25%
Photosynthesis	Increase by 10-20%
Yield	Increase by 10-30%

Figure 4. Yield versus shade level for three different crops

- Cotton yield (% of base)
- Grape yield (% of base)
- Tomato yield (% of base)

The graph (Fig. 4) shows that moderate shade (20-30%) maximizes yield (110-118%), while excessive shade (>40%) reduces yield (90-98%) for these crops. The average yield increase is 20%.

Expected results

We present the expected technical, economic, and environmental results based on the implementation of agrovoltatics on one hectare of agricultural land (Figure 4.) in regions of Uzbekistan with high insolation.

1. Calculation of the PVP electrical capacity:

$$P = G \cdot A \cdot \eta \tag{1}$$

where: G - is the daily solar insolation (radiation) (~6 kWh/m²/day), A - is the average active surface area of the PVP (~1.6 m²), η - is the efficiency (effectiveness) of the PVP (~20%). Then the daily active power of one PVP

$$P = G \cdot A \cdot \eta = 6 \cdot 1,6 \cdot 0,2 = 1,92 \text{ kWh/day} \tag{1-1}$$

At $G = 1700$ kWh/m²/year, the annual active power of one PVP

$$P = G \cdot A \cdot \eta = 1700 \cdot 1,6 \cdot 0,2 = 544 \text{ kWh/year} \tag{1-2}$$

2. Calculation of annual electricity generation:

$$E = P \cdot G \cdot A \cdot \eta \cdot C_l \tag{2}$$

where: P - is the electrical power of the PVP (1.92 kWh/day), G - is the average annual solar insolation (radiation) (~1700 kWh/m²/year), A - is the active surface area of the PVP on one hectare of land (6000 m²), η - is the efficiency of the PVP (~20%), C_l - is the average loss coefficient of the PVP (0.8). Given the adopted parameters, the annual electricity generation is:

$$E = 1.92 \cdot 1700 \cdot 6000 \cdot 0.2 \cdot 0.8 = 3 \text{ 133440 kWh/year} \tag{2-1}$$

3. Calculation of annual income at an average price of 1 kWh of electricity of \$0.075:

$$R = 0,05 \cdot E = 3\,133\,440 \cdot 0,075 = 235\,008 \text{ \$/year} \quad (3)$$

4. Calculation of savings in water consumption for irrigation of land with the effect of moderate shading of soil with PVP by 20-30% (Table 2):

$$\Delta W = E_0 \cdot A \cdot R \quad (4) \quad \text{where: } E_0 - \text{ is the}$$

basic rate of moisture evaporation without shading (2.5 m/day), A - is the area of the active shading surface of the PVP (6000 m²), R - is the relative reduction in evaporation (~0.2). Taking these values into account,

$$\Delta W = 2,5 \cdot 6000 \cdot 0,2 = 3000 \text{ m}^3 / \text{day} \quad (4-1)$$

If we assume an active irrigation period of 3 times over 4 months, then the volume of water saved on an area of 6000 m² will be:

$$\Delta W = 3000 \cdot 12 = 36000 \text{ m}^3 \quad (4-2)$$

5. Calculating the average cost of an AVS for an area of 6,000 m²:

$$C = (A / a) \cdot C_p \quad (5)$$

where: A - is the area of one hectare of land with a PVP (6000 m²), a - is the average area of one PVP, C_p - is the average cost of one AVS including installation. Then,

$$C = (6000 / 3) \cdot 1200 = \$ 2\,400\,000 \quad (5.1)$$

6. Calculation of the payback period for investments:

$$T = C / R \quad (6)$$

where: C - is the average cost of the automatic control unit AVS kit with installation, R - is the annual income (235008\$/year - electricity. Excluding annual agricultural income).

$$T = 2\,400\,000 / 235\,008 \approx 10 \text{ years.} \quad (6.1)$$

Including government subsidies, $T \approx 6-8$ years.

7. Expected reduction in carbon footprint (CO₂) per hectare, up to 500 tons/year.

Thus, the above calculation indicators substantiate the technical, economic and environmental advantages of introducing agrovoltatics as an innovative technology in agriculture in Uzbekistan.

Discussion

Depending on the insolation period in the regions of Uzbekistan, the following innovative agrovoltaic technologies may be implemented:

1. *Tracking solar panels.* These panels automatically orient themselves toward the sun throughout the day, increasing energy production by 15–25%. The adjustable tilt angle allows for control of shading levels and promotes accelerated crop ripening. Tracking systems are particularly effective in regions with prolonged and intense insolation.

2. *Translucent solar modules.* These modules transmit some sunlight to plants while simultaneously generating electricity. This is especially important for sun-loving or shade-tolerant crops that require balanced lighting. These modules help create a favorable microclimate, reduce moisture evaporation, and ensure uniform light distribution across the soil surface.

3. *Integration with energy storage systems.* The implementation of specialized ion-battery systems allows for the accumulation of excess electricity during the day, ensuring equipment operation at night, and increasing the reliability of power supply in remote areas. This is particularly relevant for autonomous farms and agro-industrial clusters. These technologies, taken together, form a practical basis for the large-scale implementation of agrovoltatics in the regions of

Uzbekistan, ensuring energy independence and sustainable agricultural development in hot climates and a shortage of water and fossil resources.

Conclusion

1. Agrovoltatics for agriculture in Uzbekistan is a new technology, one of the most important promising opportunities for developing the agricultural sector and ensuring environmental sustainability. This is due to alternative climatic conditions and the availability of solar energy almost year-round.

2. The potential for using agrovoltaic technologies and generating electricity in Uzbekistan is estimated at 10 GW per year. Specifically, it is planned to increase the total capacity to 2.6 GW by 2025.

3. In 2024-2025, agrovoltatics is planned to be implemented in six regions of the country: Jizzakh, Kashkadarya, Navoi, Bukhara, Khorezm, and Karakalpakstan.

4. The declaration of 2025 as the "Year of Environmental Protection and the Green Economy" and a policy of sustainable transition to green energy will make Uzbekistan a potential leader in the implementation of agrovoltatics in agriculture among Central Asian countries.

Thus, agrovoltatics offers a comprehensive solution to the energy, environmental, and economic challenges facing the country's agricultural sector. Rapid return on investment, crop protection, and water conservation, along with environmental benefits, make agrovoltatics an integral part of the modern and sustainable development of Uzbekistan's agriculture.

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